

NOTES

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Electrode	Lower detection limit M	Slope of response curve mV	Response time s	Working pH range	Life of electrode month
1.	Cr ^{III} ISE	1×10^{-6}	20	15	2.8 - 7.6	8
2.	Al ^{III} ISE	5×10^{-7}	20	10	8.2 - 10.8	10

TABLE 2—SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS FOR DIFFERENT CATIONS

Sl. no.	Electrode	Ions										
		Ce ³⁺	La ³⁺	Bi ³⁺	Sb ³⁺	Fe ³⁺	Cr ³⁺	As ³⁺	Al ³⁺	Zr ⁴⁺	Pb ²⁺	Hg ²⁺
1.	Cr ^{III} ISE	0.010	0.005	0.050	0.050	0.005	—	0.005	0.001	0.0050	0.97	0.18
2.	Al ^{III} ISE	0.005	0.001	0.005	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.001	—	0.0005	0.00	0.00

was varied in the range from 1×10^{-2} to 1×10^{-7} M and the potential was recorded with respective ion-selective electrode with the help of a Philips PR 9405 M pH meter at room temperature ($23 \pm 1^\circ$). The response of each electrode was plotted against the concentration of the respective ion in a semilog graph paper. In case of Cr^{III} electrode a linear response was observed down to the concentration of 1×10^{-6} M and for the Al^{III} electrode the value was 5×10^{-7} M . Other properties like response time, pH range, age of the membrane of all the three electrodes was determined (Table 1). The selectivity coefficients were determined by the mixed solution method⁴ (Table 2).

Titration of Cr^{III}, Al^{III} ion against phosphate ion :

Both Cr^{III} and Al^{III} give precipitate with orthophosphate ion and precipitation titration between these species can be monitored with a suitable sensor^{5,6}. For the titration of the above metal ions against phosphate ion, standard solutions of the salts of Cr^{III} and Al^{III} (0.01 M) and Na₂HPO₄ (0.01 M) were prepared. The solution (5 ml) was diluted to 20 ml by double-distilled water and its electrode potential measured with the respective ISE. The solution was then titrated against Na₂HPO₄

solution and after every addition of 0.1 ml Na₂HPO₄ solution, the electrode potential was noted. The potential values were plotted against the volume of Na₂HPO₄ solution consumed in titration. A sharp rise in the titration curve was observed to occur near the end-point (Fig. 1).

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Fig. 1. Plots of potential against volume of Na₂HPO₄ solution.

Photocyclisation of *trans*-Stilbene

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THE *trans* ⇌ *cis* isomerisation of stilbene with photosensitisers take place by the transfer of energy of sensitisers to stilbene during excitation under the uv irradiation¹. The photocyclisation and photoisomerisation of *trans*-stilbene has been discussed under nitrogen laser. The laser irradiation diminishes the time period of irradiation and gives maximum yield than that of the normal uv irradiation.

Experimental

Recrystallised *trans*-stilbene (0.2 g; m.p. 123°, lit.² 125°) in cyclohexane (10 ml) with iodine (1.3 mg) was taken in the first system. The second and third systems were similarly selected by passing O₂ and N₂ (for 10 min each), respectively, in stead of iodine. Each system was exposed to N₂-laser flashes for 1 h (applied voltage, 16 kV; P_{N₂} 40 torr; 65 ~ 70 flash per min).

The irradiated product was subjected to chromatography over neutral alumina (10 g) for the first and second systems. The eluants were separately collected and the residues obtained by evaporation were subsequently recrystallised from alcohol. The irradiated reaction mixture of the third system was partially evaporated and the supernatant liquid was carefully decanted in ice-cold condition. The residue was separated using an alumina column.

Results and Discussion

The products obtained from the first and second systems were identified as phenanthrene (m.p. 97°, lit.² 97°), and that of the third system was characterised as *cis*-stilbene by the usual chemical and spectral methods.

The sensitiser used in first and second systems favour in the formation of triplets during irradiation under N₂-laser and then to phenanthrene by the transfer of excited energy of the sensitiser to *trans*-stilbene. Thus, the *trans*-stilbene first isomerises to *cis*-stilbene (the intermediate) through singlet states and then cyclises to phenanthrene by triplets. The singlet¹ and triplet² mechanisms have been discussed by many workers.

In the third system the sensitiser does not help to produce triplet states, but rather singlet states are formed. Thus, it favours the formation of *cis*-stilbene.

The singlet excitation appears to be more feasible than the triplet state at room temperature. The singlet state gets populated with the sensitiser under the N₂-laser irradiation and forms *cis*-stilbene; thus, helping for the cyclisation with the consecutive *cis*-stilbene molecule to form phenanthrene. The successive abstraction of H atoms makes easy with the oxidants like iodine and oxygen. The higher phenanthrene yield in the oxygen used (i.e., second system) shows that oxygen is a stronger oxidant than the other oxidants used in the experiment. Thus the irradiation period is shorter under N₂-laser irradiation and gives higher yield than that irradiated under normal uv light.

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Studies on 2-Azetidinones. Part-I. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(3-chloro-4-aryl-2-azetidinon-1-ylcarbamoylmethoxy)diphenylsulphones

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A large number of antibiotics contain a β -lactam heterocyclic moiety¹. Also hydroxysulphones possess therapeutic properties². Keeping this in view, we have combined the two structures and synthesised some 2-azetidinone derivatives.

p,p'-Dihydroxydiphenylsulphone was condensed with ethyl chloroacetate to get the ester (1), which was then condensed with hydrazine hydrate to obtain *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethoxy)diphenylsulphone (2). The latter was condensed with aromatic aldehydes to get the Schiff bases (3), which on treatment with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine gave substituted 2-azetidinones (4). The structural assignments of the products were based on their elemental analysis, ir and pmr spectral data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial screening of 2-azetidinone derivatives was carried out using cup-plate method³ at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus citrus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Marcasane serrata* and fungi *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus niger*.